

This is the author accepted manuscript of

Fricker BA, Boender AJ, Young LJ, Kelly AM. Not just for bonding: Nucleus accumbens oxytocin receptors facilitate huddling with strangers and feeding in male spiny mice. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*. 2025 Aug;178:107496. doi: 10.1016/j.psyneuen.2025.107496. Epub 2025 May 15. PMID: 40403453.

Not just for bonding: Nucleus accumbens oxytocin receptors facilitate huddling with strangers and feeding in male spiny mice

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Key words: oxytocin receptor, huddling, sociality, nucleus accumbens

Abstract

Although oxytocin receptors (OXTRs) in the nucleus accumbens (NAc) are well-known for their contributions to bonding in mating and parental contexts, little is known about how accumbal OT signaling modulates nonreproductive social behavior. Here we used the communal spiny mouse and viral-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 to decrease OXTR expression in the NAc of males to determine the direct contributions of accumbal OXTRs to behavior during interactions with novel, same-sex conspecifics. To determine whether NAc OXTRs specifically regulate social behaviors, feeding behavior was also assessed in a mealworm eating test. Males with reduced NAc OXTR expression exhibited less huddling with novel, same-sex conspecifics and consumed fewer mealworms compared to control males. These findings suggest that accumbal OXTRs do not specifically modulate social behaviors and that there is strong evolutionary conservation of NAc OXTR social function, such that these receptors facilitate prosocial behavior across rodent species that vary in breeding system and group structure.

1. Introduction

Oxytocin (OT) signaling is well known for modulating bonding, particularly in mating and parental contexts (Bosch and Young, 2018; Froemke and Young, 2021). Although OT receptors (OXTRs) are widely distributed throughout the brain (Freeman et al., 2020), a critical brain region for OT action that regulates prosocial behavior is the nucleus accumbens (NAc), a key node in reward circuitry (Volkow et al., 2017; Klawonn and Malenka, 2018). Indeed, OT interacts with other neuromodulators to regulate social reward. For example, OT interacts with dopamine to regulate pair bond formation in female prairie voles (Keebaugh et al., 2015) and OXTRs and serotonin 1b receptors are required for social conditioned place preference (with cagemates) in male mice (Dolen et al., 2013). Most studies examining NAc OXTR function use the socially monogamous prairie vole. For example, knockdown of accumbal OXTRs disrupts partner preference formation and reduces alloparental behavior (Keebaugh et al., 2015), whereas overexpression of OXTRs in the NAc enhances partner preference formation and alloparental care in female prairie voles (Keebaugh and Young, 2011). Notably, NAc OXTRs similarly modulate maternal care in transgenic mice (Witchev et al., 2024), demonstrating that accumbal OT-mediated prosocial behavior is not unique to voles and/or socially monogamous species. Recent studies have elucidated a more complex function of accumbal OXTRs, such that socio-sexual experience alters oxytocinergic-modulated signaling in the NAc (Borie et al., 2022) and development with or without OXTRs differentially influences NAc signaling in a sex-specific manner in prairie voles (Long et al.). To date, most studies have identified prosocial functions of NAc OXTRs in female rodents, as well as in species that are territorial in contexts outside of mating and parenting. How accumbal OT signaling modulates behavior in highly social, communal species largely remains unknown.

Spiny mice (*Acomys dimidiatus*) are a communally breeding rodent native to Africa, the Middle East, and Southeast Asia (Haughton et al., 2016). This species naturally lives in large groups (Haughton et al., 2016), and in the lab both males and females exhibit high degrees of prosociality and very low levels of aggression with conspecifics regardless of novelty/familiarity, kinship status, or reproductive context (Fricker et al., 2021; Gonzalez Abreu et al., 2022; Fricker et al., 2023). Spiny mice also welcome unrelated newcomers to an established group (Cizkova et al., 2011). Therefore, spiny mice are an excellent organism for examining the contributions of accumbal OT signaling to prosocial behavior in nonreproductive contexts, particularly with strangers. We previously mapped OXTR distributions throughout the basal forebrain and midbrain of spiny mice and found that they exhibit robust OXTR expression in the NAc (Powell et al., 2022). While there has been no direct comparison of spiny mouse NAc OXTR expression with other mammals, species such as prairie voles, California mice, and Sprague-Dawley rats show OXTR expression in both the shell and core of NAc (Bernheim et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2020; Inoue et al., 2022), whereas OXTR expression is largely restricted to the NAc shell of spiny mice (Powell et al., 2022). Further, although NAc OXTR densities distinguish mating systems in voles, with monogamous prairie voles having more NAc OXTRs than polygamous montane voles (Insel and Shapiro, 1992), eusocial naked mole rats (a non-monogamous rodent) also exhibit robust NAc OXTR expression (Mooney et al., 2015; Freeman et al., 2020). The dense OXTR binding observed in species like naked mole rats and spiny mice demonstrates that NAc OXTR function is not restricted to behaviors associated with monogamy.

Although, to our knowledge, no studies have examined the role of nonpeptide receptors in spiny mouse behavior, we previously examined a role for OT in social behavior for this species. OT neurons in the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus (PVN) are more responsive to interactions with a novel, same-sex conspecific compared to a novel object (i.e., rubber duck); additionally, PVN OT neural responses positively correlate with nonreproductive prosocial behavior with a stranger as well as with tyrosine hydroxylase neural responses in the ventral tegmental area (Gonzalez Abreu et al., 2022). These findings suggest that PVN OT may gate social reward in nonreproductive contexts via connections with reward circuitry in spiny mice. Indeed, retrobead tracing demonstrated that PVN OT neurons send axonal

projections to the VTA (Gonzalez Abreu et al., 2022) and the NAc (unpub obs) of spiny mice, as has been observed in lab mice (Xiao et al., 2017; He et al., 2021). This prior data in spiny mice suggests that the OT system may modulate social reward in this species. Yet, how accumbal OT signaling contributes toward behavior in spiny mice remains unknown.

Here we used viral-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 to decrease OXTR expression in the NAc of male spiny mice (previously validated in Boender et al. (Boender et al., 2023)) to determine the direct contributions of accumbal OXTRs to behavior during interactions with novel conspecifics. We previously found that male spiny mice are more prosocial with novel kin than novel non-kin in a complex group interaction (Fricker et al., 2023) and, therefore, tested subjects in social interaction tests with novel kin as well as novel non-kin. To determine whether NAc OXTRs modulate affiliative preferences with strangers, we also conducted a social preference test where subjects had the choice of interacting with a novel kin or novel non-kin same-sex conspecific. Lastly, to examine whether NAc OXTRs specifically modulate behavior associated with *social* contexts, we conducted a giant mealworm eating test. Although prior studies have shown that central administration of OT reduces feeding (Sabatier et al., 2013), extremely few studies have specifically examined the influence of NAc OXTRs on feeding behavior. If NAc OXTRs facilitate prosocial behavior across species, then these receptors will modulate prosocial behaviors like huddling in the communal spiny mouse outside the contexts of mating/pair bonding and parenting. Thus, we hypothesized that spiny mice with reduced OXTR expression in the NAc would exhibit less prosocial behavior with strangers compared to control animals. Because spiny mice may find interactions with novel kin more rewarding than with novel non-kin (Fricker et al., 2023), we predicted that a reduction in NAc OXTRs would abolish a preference to affiliate with novel kin. Further, because conditional knockout of NAc OXTRs in female mice does not influence feeding in the homecage (Witchev et al., 2024), we predicted that a reduction of NAc OXTR expression in spiny mice would not influence consumption of giant mealworms.

2. Methods

2.1 Animals

24 adult male (post-natal day (PND) 250-500; ages were evenly distributed across treatment groups) spiny mice (*Acomys dimidiatus*) from our breeding colony were used as subjects for the study; males were randomly assigned to either an OXTR knockdown group or a control group. Sex was determined by examination of external genitalia. All animals were group-housed (2-3) in standard rat polycarbonate cages (40.64cm X 20.32cm X 20.32cm) that contained Sani-Chips bedding. Spiny mice were provided with rodent igloos and shepherd shacks and were able to obtain food and water ad libitum. Animals were kept on a 14-h light:10-h dark cycle with an ambient temperature of $24 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The circadian rhythm of *Acomys* species can vary depending on environmental conditions (Levy et al., 2007; Cohen et al., 2009); spiny mice in our colony exhibit diurnal activity patterns and were therefore tested during the day under the light phase. All procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee of Emory University. Due to a lack of female spiny mouse availability in our colony, we were only able to conduct this study in males. Therefore, future studies are needed to examine the contribution of NAc OXTRs to female spiny mouse behavior. 4 animals were removed from the dataset due to inaccurate surgical targeting, resulting in a final sample size of 10 males in the OXTR knockdown group (AAV- Δ OXTR) and 10 males in the control group (AAV-CTRL).

2.2 Experimental Design

Subjects were randomly assigned to either an AAV- Δ OXTR (i.e., OXTR knockdown) group or an AAV-CTRL (i.e., control) group. After 4-6 weeks of viral incubation, subjects underwent behavioral testing for two days. Subjects were tested in two tests a day, with 1-2 hours in-between tests. Behavioral tests

included: (1) a social interaction with a novel, same-sex kin conspecific, (2) a social interaction with a novel, same-sex non-kin conspecific, (3) a social preference test, and (4) a mealworm eating test. The order of behavior tests was randomized across subjects.

Figure 1. NAc surgical targeting and CRISPR/Cas9 AAV efficacy. (A) Schematic illustrating viral-induced enhanced green fluorescent protein (eGFP) fluorescence in a spiny mouse subject (left) and representative section from the Allen Mouse Brain Atlas (right). Note that spiny mouse brains are shaped slightly differently than lab mouse brains. (B) A representative autoradiogram from a spiny mouse from the prior validation study (Boender et al., 2023) demonstrating OXTR expression reduction on the side of the brain injected with AAV- Δ OXTR but not on the side of the brain injected with AAV-CTRL.

2.3 Stereotaxic Injections

Subjects in the OXTR knockdown group received intracranial injections targeting the NAc of a CRISPR/Cas9 AAV targeting the gRNA Δ OXTR.2 sequence (referred to as AAV- Δ OXTR; **Figure 1A**), whereas subjects in the control group received injections of a control AAV-gRNA (referred to as AAV-CTRL). These viruses were previously generated and validated in the NAc of spiny mice, with the AAV- Δ OXTR significantly reducing OXTR expression compared to the AAV-CTRL (Boender et al., 2023). From this validation study, the hemisphere that expressed the AAV- Δ OXTR exhibited 95% less OXTR binding compared to the control hemisphere (Boender et al., 2023)(**Figure 1B**). Spiny mice received a 1.5mg/kg dose of meloxicam orally 30 minutes prior to anesthetization with 4% isoflurane and were maintained with 2% isoflurane during the surgery. Subjects were fitted onto a stereotax (Sotocinal et al.) and all AAVs were delivered via a pulled glass pipette at a rate of 1nl/sec using a nanosyringe (Drummond Nanoject III). 250nL of virus was injected at each site. Pipettes were held at the injection site for 10 min following AAV release. Coordinates (referenced to Bregma) for bilaterally targeting the NAc were: 2.55mm anterior, \pm 0.80mm lateral, 4.70mm depth and 2.95mm anterior, \pm 0.65mm lateral, 4.60mm depth. Viral vectors were allowed to express for 4-6 weeks prior to behavioral testing. During this time, all subjects were group-housed with 1-2 other untreated, same-sex littermates. Confirmation of surgical targeting was confirmed by the presence of fluorescent virus; only subjects with accurate targeting of the NAc and no viral spread were retained for analyses. It should be noted that the eGFP and Cas9 viruses are premixed and are therefore co-injected through the same needle, and thus the spread of eGFP and Cas9 should be similar. However, it is possible that some cells may contain eGFP but no Cas9 and vice versa; such cells likely represent a small minority as this tool achieves >90% knockdown over the whole area of eGFP positive tissue (Boender et al., 2023). Although not perfect, based on our observations, the fluorescent signal gives an adequate indication as to whether the right area of the brain was targeted, as was previously demonstrated by Boender and colleagues (Boender et al., 2023). Accurate surgical targeting for all subjects was determined by examination of viral eGFP labeling *post mortem*; note that the

AAVs contained an eGFP tag. Surgical targeting was considered an accurate “hit” if eGFP was detected only around the NAc where OXTRs are present as indicated in Figure 1. 4 animals exhibited mistargeting and/or viral leakage from when the glass pipette was removed from the brain after injection (i.e., creating a trail of virus from the NAc to the top of the cortex); these 4 animals were removed from the dataset.

2.4 Social Interactions Tests

To determine the contribution of NAc OXTRs to behavior during freely behaving interactions with novel conspecifics, subjects underwent two social interaction tests – one with a novel, same-sex kin conspecific and one with a novel, same-sex non-kin conspecific. The subject and an age- and weight-matched stimulus animal were simultaneously placed into a clean rat cage via plastic beakers and were allowed to freely interact for 10 min. The cages contained no enrichment or food/water. Tests were video recorded using Sony Handycam cameras. Stimulus animals were previously marked with a rodent marker to distinguish subjects from stimuli in video recordings. Huddling, investigation, and autogrooming were scored using BORIS (Friard and Gamba, 2016). Huddling was defined as the subject and stimulus animal resting together with bodies touching and/or overlapping. Investigation was defined as the subject’s nose making contact with (i.e., sniffing) the head, flank, or rear of the stimulus animal. No aggression (i.e., chasing, biting, lunging) was observed for any animal.

2.5 Social Preference Test

To examine whether male spiny mice exhibit a preference for spending time near or investigating a novel, same-sex kin conspecific or a novel, same-sex non-kin conspecific, subjects were tested in a social preference test. The testing chamber (previously used in (Fricker et al., 2024)) consisted of an initial acrylic chamber (15.24cm X 15.24cm X 45.72cm) that releases subjects into a large, opaque acrylic chamber (55.88cm X 71.12cm X 45.72cm) divided into two identical sections. Each section can hold up to 8 stimulus animals or objects, separated from the subject by clear acrylic with 0.12 cm diameter holes. When the subject is in one section, their view of the other section is entirely obstructed. One section contained a novel, same-sex kin conspecific whereas the other section contained a novel, same-sex non-kin conspecific. For a schematic of the chamber, see **Figure S1**. Stimulus sides were randomized across subjects to account for any side biases. For the preference test, the subject was transferred via a beaker into the initial chamber. Once released into the large chamber, the subject was allowed to freely explore for 10 min. Tests were video recorded, and the amount of time spent near each stimulus animal and the time spent investigating each stimulus animal (i.e., subject’s nose made contact with the walls containing a stimulus animal) was scored in BORIS. Ethovision XT 17 (Noldus, Virginia, USA) was used for automated tracking to obtain the distanced traveled and velocity during the 10 min test.

2.6 Mealworm Eating Test

To determine whether NAc OXTRs modulate nonsocial behavior in male spiny mice, subjects underwent a mealworm eating test. Spiny mice eagerly consume mealworms,; mealworms are provided as enrichment to spiny mice in our colony once a month. For the test, subjects were transferred via a beaker into one side of a medium acrylic chamber (81.28cm X 30.48cm X 40.64cm) that contained a weigh-boat of 10 same-length, giant mealworms at the opposite end of the chamber. The number of mealworms consumed during a 10 min period was recorded.

2.7 Histology

After behavioral testing, subjects were euthanized via isoflurane overdose and were transcardially perfused with 0.1M phosphate buffered saline (PBS) followed by 4% paraformaldehyde dissolved in 0.1M borate buffer (pH 9.5). Brains were post-fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde overnight before

cryoprotection in 30% sucrose dissolved in PBS for 48 h. Brains were sectioned at 40um using a Leica cryostat. The AAVs contain an eGFP tag, and thus surgical targeting was confirmed *post mortem* on a Zeiss AxioImager II microscope.

2.8 Statistics

Social interaction tests were analyzed using linear mixed models (LMMs) with Treatment (AAV-CTRL or AAV- Δ OXTR) and Stimulus Type (kin or non-kin) as fixed factors and Subject as a random factor to account for repeated testing. Social interaction data analyzed for control subjects only was analyzed with Wilcoxon Signed Ranks tests. Data for the social preference test and feeding test were normally distributed and therefore analyzed using independent t-tests or paired sample t-tests. All posthoc pairwise comparison were corrected using the Sidak correction. All data were analyzed using SPSS 29 (IBM Analytics, USA) and graphs were made using Prism 10 (GraphPad, USA).

3. Results

3.1 OXTRs in the NAc facilitate huddling with novel, same-sex strangers

To determine the contributions of NAc OXTRs to behavior during social interactions with novel, same-sex conspecifics, male spiny mice were tested in two social interaction tests – one with a novel kin and another with a novel non-kin conspecific. A linear mixed model (LMM) with Treatment (AAV-CTRL or AAV- Δ OXTR) and Stimulus Type (kin or non-kin) as fixed factors and Subject as a random factor yielded a main effect of Treatment for huddling ($F_{(36)} = 6.61$, $p = 0.01$; **Figure 2A**), with AAV- Δ OXTR subjects that had the NAc OXTR population knocked down exhibiting less huddling behavior with novel conspecifics, regardless of whether they were kin or non-kin. We observed no effects of or interactions with Stimulus Type (all $p > 0.36$) on huddling. Additionally, we found no effects of or interactions between Treatment and Stimulus Type for investigative behavior (all $p > 0.32$; see **Figure 2B** as an example for the lack of effect of Treatment). However, we did find that NAc OXTRs influenced autogrooming during social interactions. A main effect of Treatment ($F_{(18)} = 7.94$, $p = 0.01$; **Figure 2C**) revealed that AAV- Δ OXTR subjects exhibited more autogrooming than control subjects, whereas Stimulus Type did not influence autogrooming (all $p > 0.64$). Although we did not observe an influence of Stimulus Type for any of the behaviors examined, behavior broken down by Stimulus Type can be found in **Figure S2**.

Figure 2. Social Interaction Test. (A) Compared to male spiny mice in the AAV-CTRL group (cream), AAV- Δ OXTR males (sage green) spent less time huddling with a novel, same-sex conspecific. (B) Investigation of stimulus animals did not differ between AAV-CTRL and AAV- Δ OXTR males. (C) AAV- Δ OXTR subjects spent more time autogrooming than AAV-CTRL animals. Note that data from the two social interaction tests (one with kin

(black dots), one with non-kin (maroon dots)) are combined here to reflect the LMM main effect of Treatment. Individual dots represent subjects; each subject has two dots, one black and one maroon, per bar. Data are represented as mean \pm SEM. An asterisk indicates statistical significance of $p = 0.01$.

We previously found that male spiny mice were more prosocial with novel kin than novel, non-kin (Fricker et al., 2023). Because we did not observe any effects of or interactions with Stimulus Type in the LMMs that included all subjects, we specifically examined whether spiny mice exhibited differences in huddling or investigation with novel kin and non-kin only in control subjects. However, a Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test showed no differences between kin and non-kin for huddling ($z = -0.56$, $p = 0.58$), investigation ($z = -0.26$, $p = 0.80$), or a combined prosocial metric (i.e., huddling and investigation, as was previously used in Fricker et al. [15]) ($z = -0.45$, $p = 0.88$). This lack of replication of our previous finding is discussed below in the Discussion.

3.2 Male spiny mice do not exhibit a preference for novel kin or novel non-kin in a social preference test

Because no studies have specifically examined whether spiny mice exhibit a preference for novel kin or novel non-kin in a preference test, male subjects were run in a social preference test in which they had the choice to investigate and/or spend time near a novel, same-sex kin peer or a novel, same-sex non-kin peer. In control subjects only, we observed no difference in the time spent investigating ($t(9) = -0.14$, $p = 0.45$) or near ($t(9) = 0.05$, $p = 0.48$) either stimulus animal, suggesting that males either do not have a preference for novel kin or novel non-kin or that we did not detect any such preference in our test. To further examine whether NAc OXTR knockdown influences behavior in the social preference test, we generated normalized preference scores (e.g., (time investigating kin minus time investigating non-kin) divided by (time investigating kin plus time investigating non-kin); same equation for time near stimuli). Independent t-tests yielded no differences between control and AAV- Δ OXTR subjects for a near preference score ($t(18) = -0.15$, $p = 0.44$; **Figure 3A**) or an investigation preference score ($t(18) = 0.58$, $p = 0.29$; **Figure 3B**). Together these findings suggest that male spiny mice do not exhibit a preference for novel kin or novel non-kin and that knockdown of NAc OXTRs does not induce such a preference.

Figure 3. Social Preference Test. AAV-CTRL males and AAV- Δ OXTR males did not exhibit a difference in (A) affiliation preferences (time spent near novel kin or novel non-kin stimulus animals) or (B) investigation preferences (time spent investigating novel kin or novel non-kin stimulus animals).

Since subjects were the only animals in the social preference test to freely explore the chamber, we measured distance traveled and velocity during the 10 min test to determine whether NAc OXTR knockdown influences movement behavior. Independent t-tests showed no difference between control and AAV- Δ OXTR subjects for distance traveled ($t(18) = -0.22$, $p = 0.41$; **Figure 4A**) or velocity ($t(18) = -0.08$, $p = 0.47$; **Figure 4B**).

Figure 4. Movement Behavior. AAV-CTRL males (cream) and AAV-ΔOXTR males (sage green) did not exhibit a difference in (A) distance traveled or (B) or velocity during the 10 min Social Preference Test.

3.3 OXTRs in the NAc facilitate eating mealworms

To test whether NAc OXTRs regulate nonsocial behavior, we observed the number of mealworms consumed during a 10 min period. An independent t-test revealed that AAV-ΔOXTR subjects ate significantly fewer mealworms compared to control subjects ($t(18) = 2.80, p < 0.01$); **Figure 5**). This demonstrates that OXTRs in the NAc modulate behavior outside of a social context.

Figure 5. Mealworm Eating Test. Male spiny mice in the AAV-CTRL group (cream) ate more mealworms than AAV-ΔOXTR males (sage green) during a 10 min period. Individual dots represent subjects. Data are represented as mean ± SEM. An asterisk indicates statistical significance.

4. Discussion

In the present study we found that male spiny mice with a viral-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 reduction of OXTR expression in the NAc huddled less with same-sex strangers, regardless of kinship status, compared to control males. Additionally, accumbal OXTR knockdown also resulted in more autogrooming and the consumption of fewer mealworms, demonstrating that these receptors also modulate nonsocial behaviors. Together, these findings provide novel insight into OT signaling in the NAc and show that accumbal OXTRs facilitate huddling with strangers in a communal species that is typically prosocial in nonreproductive contexts.

4.1 NAc OXTRs and social behavior

Several studies over the last few decades have examined the involvement of OT signaling in the nucleus accumbens in relation to pair bonding and have begun to elegantly home in on nuanced contributions of

accumbal OT to neuromodulation and behavior. Early studies identified that NAc OXTR densities reflected breeding structure in rodents, such that monogamous prairie voles express significantly more accumbal OXTRs than non-monogamous meadow voles, rats, and mice (Insel and Shapiro, 1992; Olazabal and Young, 2006). Subsequent studies found that antagonism of OXTRs in the NAc prevented mating-induced partner preference formation in prairie voles (Young et al., 2001), and knockdown of NAc OXTRs via RNA interference disrupted partner preference formation in female prairie voles (Keebaugh et al., 2015). More recent studies in prairie voles have revealed that OT signaling in the NAc is changed through social experience in a sex-specific manner (Borie et al., 2022) and that OXTRs modulate calcium signaling in the NAc in a sex-specific manner (Long et al.). These studies provide enhanced cellular resolution for understanding how NAc OXTRs promote prosocial behavior toward pair bond partners. In addition to an examination of pair bonding, studies have also examined a role for accumbal OT in modulating parental care. OXTR antagonism in the NAc blocked spontaneous maternal care in prairie voles (Olazabal and Young, 2006) and knockout of NAc OXTRs prevented the onset of maternal behavior in transgenic mice (Witchev et al., 2024). Similarly, chemogenetic inhibition of the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus (PVN) to NAc OT circuit inhibited paternal care in mandarin voles (He et al., 2021).

Here we expand upon research that supports a role for accumbal OXTRs in bonding in reproductive contexts and demonstrate that NAc OT signaling also contributes toward nonreproductive prosocial behavior in a highly social, large group-living species – the spiny mouse. Notably, a prior study in California mice also examined NAc OXTR contributions to nonreproductive social behavior; somewhat similar to our findings here, this study found that antagonism of OXTRs in the NAc in male and female California mice reduced social approach of novel same-sex stimuli that were behind a barrier (Williams et al., 2020). It is worth considering that social approach in this context may not necessarily result in a prosocial outcome given that California mice are a territorial species and are typically aggressive with novel, same-sex conspecifics (Rieger and Marler, 2018). Although it is not in the behavioral repertoire of this territorial species to frequently engage in prosocial interactions with novel peers, it is likely highly adaptable to approach novel conspecifics to gain information. Thus, OT signaling in the NAc may facilitate context-appropriate social behaviors in a species-specific manner. Whereas OXTRs in this brain region promote nonreproductive social approach in territorial California mice, they facilitate nonreproductive huddling in communal spiny mice. This is consistent with the social salience hypothesis of OT, which posits that OT regulates the salience of social cues and will thus influence behavior in a manner dependent on context and individual (and/or species) characteristics (Shamay-Tsoory and Abu-akel, 2015). Relatedly, pharmacological studies have shown that an infusion of an OXTR antagonist into the NAc of lab mice prevents a social conditioned place preference, demonstrating that accumbal OT signaling is involved in social reward (Dolen et al., 2013). Although NAc OXTR-mediated behavior may be somewhat different across species, accumbal OXTR influences on behavior fit within a framework of having a general involvement in social reward. Pair bonding is rewarding for socially monogamous prairie voles (Sadino and Donaldson, 2024), affiliating with novel peers in communal spiny mice is presumably rewarding (Fricker et al., 2021; Gonzalez Abreu et al., 2022), and given that aggression can also be rewarding (Golden et al., 2017), approaching and potentially aggressing against novel, same-sex conspecifics may also be rewarding for territorial California mice (Greenberg et al., 2015). Further, prairie voles that have higher NAc OXTR binding densities exhibit great social motivation as assessed by lever pressing to gain access to a partner (Beery et al., 2021). Together, this body of literature suggests that NAc OXTRs evolved species-specific functions to promote context-appropriate behavior associated with social reward.

As noted earlier, spiny mice express OXTRs primarily in the shell of the NAc (Powell et al., 2022). Although not specific to OT signaling, the NAc shell has been associated with arousing aspects of motivation, whereas the NAc core modulates goal-direct motivational behaviors (Corbit et al., 2001; Di Chiara, 2002). Additionally, studies show that the shell is required for mediating the influence of context

on reward-seeking behavior (Chaudhri et al., 2010; Ito and Hayen, 2011). Together with the consideration of the social salience hypothesis of OT (Shamay-Tsoory and Abu-akel, 2015), accumbal OXTRs in spiny mice may facilitate distinguishing context and, either directly or indirectly, promote context-appropriate responses, such as consuming calorie-rich food when it is available and huddling with novel, same-sex conspecifics – an adaptive social behavior for a group-living species that evolved to aggregate rather than be solitary. Although tracing studies mapping connections to and from the NAc in spiny mice have not been systematically conducted, studies in Sprague Dawley rats and transgenic mice demonstrate that the NAc shell receives dopaminergic and glutamatergic inputs from the VTA (Yamaguchi et al., 2011; Qi et al., 2016; Yu et al., 2019). Further, PVN OT neurons send projections to accumbens in spiny mice (unpub obs), transgenic mice, and prairie voles (Ross et al., 2009; Nardou et al., 2019). Because dopamine and OT interact in NAc to facilitate pair bonding in prairie voles (Liu and Wang, 2003), it is feasible that the reduction of OXTRs in the shell of spiny mice disrupted dopaminergic and OT interactions that may promote bonding and/or general prosociality in spiny mice, hence our observation of reduced huddling with strangers in CRISPR-induced OXTR knockdown animals. Additional studies in spiny mice are needed to differentiate contributions of the accumbens shell and core to behavior, and to disentangle how OT interacts with other neural systems to modulate complex aspects of reward and motivation.

In the present study we did not observe a preference for novel, same-sex kin or non-kin as tested in a social preference test. To our knowledge, this was the first time such a social preference test has been conducted in spiny mice and suggests that male spiny mice do not exhibit a preference for kin over non-kin in a nonreproductive context. However, we previously found that male spiny mice are more prosocial with same-sex novel kin than non-kin in a social interaction test in which animals are freely interacting (Fricker et al., 2023). Consistent with our social preference test findings, we also did not observe any differences in behavior when subjects interacted with kin or non-kin in the social interaction tests. Notably, in our previous study, prosocial behavior was quantified as the time spent huddling *and* investigating conspecifics, whereas in the present study investigation and huddling were analyzed separately. Yet even a combination of these behaviors here did not replicate our previous finding. The lack of replication of our previous findings could be due to various factors including seasonality and age. The age range of our previous study included younger adults. Additionally, while *Acomys dimidiatus* exhibits seasonal breeding in the wild, with a preference to copulate after long rains, in the lab this species breeds year-round but typically produce more pups in the spring (Haughton et al., 2016); experiments from our previous study were conducted in the summer and fall, whereas the current study was conducted in the spring. Future studies are thus required to determine if age and/or seasonality influence kin-biased behavior. Notably, we have conducted other types of social preference tests in male and female spiny mice using this exact apparatus as well as similar testing chambers, and spiny mice do exhibit social preferences, including a preference for larger over smaller groups, as well as sex-specific preferences for affiliating with same- or opposite- sex conspecifics (Fricker et al., 2021; Gonzalez Abreu et al., 2022; Fricker et al., 2024). These prior findings demonstrate that spiny mice exhibit some social preferences, which can be assessed in tests like that used in the present study. Given that the brain differentially processes novel kin from novel non-kin in spiny mice (Fricker et al., 2023) and rats (Clemens et al., 2020), it is likely that the subjects in our present study were able to differentiate between conspecific identities despite our lack of detecting any behavioral differences toward those distinct conspecific types. Prior research has shown that OT signaling does modulate behavior in relation to the kinship status of a conspecific. For example, intranasal OT enhances kinship recognition in women (Fischer-Shofty et al., 2013), and OT administration enhances recognition of offspring in sheep and prairie voles (Bielsky and Young, 2004). More broadly, OT also facilitates general social recognition (Oettl et al., 2016). Because we did not observe a difference in behavior directed toward kin and non-kin, we cannot conclude whether NAc OXTRs are or are not involved in kin recognition or kin-biased behavior in spiny mice.

4.2 NAc OXTRs and nonsocial behavior

Few studies have specifically sought to examine whether accumbal OT signaling modulates nonsocial behaviors despite numerous studies demonstrating that OT is involved in nonsocial behaviors such as feeding, stress, and anxiety responses (Sabatier et al., 2013; Yoon and Kim, 2020). Interestingly, most studies have shown that OT has anorexigenic properties and that central administration of OT reduces food intake (Sabatier et al., 2013). However, our findings here contradict this, such that knockdown of NAc OXTRs in spiny mice reduced the number of mealworms consumed during a 10 min period. This also stands in contrast to findings in female transgenic mice that were actively caring for offspring, in which knockout of NAc OXTRs did not influence feeding behavior (Witchev et al., 2024). These contradictory findings may be partially explained by variation in social/environmental context across studies given that a study in rats found that injection of OT into the NAc had anorexigenic effects only in a nonsocial setting and that a social context abolished the accumbal OT effects on feeding (Herisson et al., 2016). The feeding test in the present study was conducted in a nonsocial setting (i.e., spiny mice were alone in the test cage), however, it is also worth considering that our methods of central manipulation are quite different from those used in rats by Herisson et al. Our results show that NAc OXTRs facilitate consumption of mealworms (a presumably rewarding treat) in spiny mice, suggesting that viral-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 reduction of OXTR expression in the NAc may have globally (i.e., not restricted to a social context) decreased motivation and/or interfered with reward processing. Notably, we did not food-deprive our subjects, and thus there may have been individual variation in motivation to eat mealworms. However, mealworms are a rare treat for spiny mice in our colony, and we have never observed an unmanipulated spiny mouse refuse to eat mealworms when presented with the option to eat such a treat; spiny mice are used as a model for diabetes because they have a tendency to overeat (Shafir, 2000), so it is possible that they may consume rare, calorie-rich treats regardless of being satiated from having recently eaten rodent chow in the home cage. Importantly, though, our experimental design did not directly assess motivation in spiny mice given that animals were not required to exert effort to gain access to stimuli. Thus, future studies are required to determine the role of accumbal OXTRs in nonsocial rewarding behaviors such as feeding.

In mammals, OT has anxiogenic and anti-stress effects (Neumann and Landgraf, 2012; Uvnas-Moberg et al., 2014). For example, OT is released in response to stroking or touch (Uvnas-Moberg et al., 2014), and thus self-grooming has been interpreted as a means to cope with stress and anxiety (Estanislau et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2021). Indeed, OT infusion into the PVN initiates autogrooming in rats (Van Erp et al., 1993). However, a study in prairie voles found that males administered a high dose of intranasal OT autogroomed less than those administered lower doses (Bales et al., 2013). These findings in male voles are more consistent with our observation of increased autogrooming in spiny mice that had fewer accumbal OXTRs. The observation of increased autogrooming in spiny mice with NAc OXTR knockdown may reflect an indirect effect of knockdown, such that NAc OXTRs may not directly contribute toward grooming behavior, and instead enhanced autogrooming may have been the result of stress and/or anxiety associated with other consequences of accumbal OXTR knockdown. For example, given that spiny mice are highly social, spending less time affiliating with a conspecific, and thus spending more time alone, may have served as a stressor by which knockdown animals coped with via autogrooming. Notably, conditional knockout of NAc OXTRs in female transgenic mice did not influence grooming behavior (Witchev et al., 2024), and therefore there may simply be species and/or sex differences in the modulation of grooming behavior.

5. Conclusion

This study provides novel insight into the range of social behaviors influenced by NAc OXTRs. Here we demonstrated that NAc OXTRs facilitate prosocial behavior outside of reproductive contexts, such as bonding with mates or offspring, by showing that NAc OXTRs promote huddling with strangers in male

spiny mice. Because prosocial behavior with novel conspecifics is a context-appropriate behavior for many highly social, communal species, like spiny mice, these results provide support for the social salience hypothesis of OT. Additionally, our findings suggest that there is strong evolutionary conservation of NAc OXTR function, such that these receptors facilitate prosocial behavior across rodent species that vary in breeding system and group structure, but that adaptations have evolved to facilitate species-specific behavior. Lastly, the observation that OXTR knockdown in the NAc influenced feeding and self-grooming suggests that receptors in this region modulate nonsocial behavior, either directly or indirectly. These findings enhance our understanding of the complexities of accumbal OT-mediated behavior.

Acknowledgements

We thank Nicklas Gose for assistance with Ethovision. We would also like to mourn the recent passing of Dr. Larry J. Young. Dr. Young was an advocate for conducting research in a broad range of species. His tireless efforts to promote prairie voles as a novel model organism for studying social monogamy inspired Dr. Kelly to use a species (i.e., spiny mice) new to the field of social neuroscience for pursuing questions related to nonreproductive sociality and group living. Dr. Young also served as an inspirational mentor to Dr. Boender for over 7 years. This work is a testament to Dr. Young's collaborative spirit, and we are honored to have been able to work with such an outstanding scientist.

Author contributions

B.A.F.: conceptualization, data curation, methodology, investigation, writing – reviewing and editing; A.J.B.: methodology, writing – reviewing and editing; L.J.Y.: methodology; A.M.K.: conceptualization, investigation, formal analysis, project administration, funding acquisition, supervision, writing – original draft.

Funding

This work was supported by the National Science Foundation (IOS-2310626 to AMK). BAF was supported by the Department of Defense through the National Defense Science and Engineering Graduate Fellowship Program.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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